

Non-Abelian extensions of the tetrads and the spin-connections; Associated Actions

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Abstract

We propose a non-abelian extension of the tetrad and spin-connection formulation of gravity by promoting the tetrads e_μ^a and spin connections ω_μ^{ab} to fields carrying an additional group index i . In this way, the standard tetrads and the associated Ricci rotation coefficients acquire an internal gauge structure. Starting from the first-order Palatini action, we investigate the construction of a corresponding theory for the $\mathbf{SU(3)}$ group. We find that an action based on the conventional antisymmetric structure constants f^{ijk} does not lead to a consistent formulation. The search for a viable extension instead points to a different algebraic structure involving the totally symmetric $\mathbf{SU(3)}$ constants d^{ijk} . A scalar quantity E emerges naturally within this framework. In many respects, it plays a role analogous to that of the tetrad determinant e in ordinary gravity and constitutes a relevant ingredient of the construction. At this stage, our goal is to introduce the basic geometrical and algebraic structures underlying the proposal. As a concrete illustration, we present the explicit realization associated with the $\mathbf{SU(3)}$ group, leaving a more detailed investigation of its physical and mathematical implications for future work.

The Palatini action [1], first order tetrad gravity depends on the tetrads e_μ^a and the spin connections ω_μ^{ab} (Ricci rotation coefficients); through variation, the spin connections become dependent on the tetrads.

In this work, the construction of non-abelian fields [2] $(e_\mu^a)^i$ and $(\omega_\mu^{ab})^i$ is considered, where the index i corresponds to the non-abelian group of interest. We will construct the action for the $SU(3)$ case.

Our construction is based on the Palatini action and is expressed in terms of the fields $(e_\mu^a)^i$, and a generalized Riemann tensor $(R_{\mu\nu}{}^{ab})^i$, which is a function of the $(\omega_\mu^{ab})^i$ fields. A scalar E arises and can be understood as a generalization of the standard determinant of the tetrads.

We briefly discuss how similar proposals can be constructed for the Ashtekar [3], and MacDowell-Mansouri [4] actions; an associated supergravity [5] can also be formulated.

At this stage, our construction is essentially formal, and any interpretation regarding the meaning or existence at these new fields remains speculative. We begin by considering the Palatini action

$$S \sim \int d^4x e e^\mu{}_a e^\nu{}_b R_{\mu\nu}{}^{ab}, \quad (1)$$

where e_μ^a are tetrads, e is their determinant and

$$R_{\mu\nu}{}^{ab} = \partial_\mu \omega_\nu{}^{ab} - \partial_\nu \omega_\mu{}^{ab} + \omega_\mu{}^a{}_c \omega_\nu{}^{cb} - \omega_\nu{}^a{}_c \omega_\mu{}^{cb}, \quad (2)$$

where ω_μ^{ab} , denotes the Ricci notation coefficients.

The determinant of the tetrads given by

$$e = \frac{1}{4!} \varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \varepsilon_{abcd} e_\mu^a e_\nu^b e_\rho^c e_\sigma^d, \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ and ε_{abcd} are Levi-Civita symbols. Substitution of the determinant (3) in action (1), results in

$$S \sim \int d^4x \varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \varepsilon_{abcd} e_\mu^a e_\nu^b R_{\rho\sigma}{}^{cd}. \quad (4)$$

We now depart from action (4) to propose the following action

$$S \sim \int d^4x \varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \varepsilon_{abcd} d_{ijk} (e_\mu^a)^j (e_\nu^b)^k (R_{\rho\sigma}{}^{cd})^i, \quad (5)$$

where d_{ijk} is the totally symmetric invariant tensor of the SU(3) group. The fields $(e_\mu^a)^i$ are gauge fields that extend the usual tetrad field, and

$$(R_{\rho\sigma}{}^{cd})^i = \partial_\rho (\omega_\sigma{}^{cd})^i - \partial_\sigma (\omega_\rho{}^{cd})^i + \bar{g} d_{ijk} \left[(\omega_\rho{}^c{}_f)^j (\omega_\sigma{}^{fd})^k - (\omega_\sigma{}^c{}_f)^j (\omega_\rho{}^{fd})^k \right], \quad (6)$$

where \bar{g} is an appropriate coupling constant, the $(\omega_\rho{}^{cd})^i$ are gauge fields themselves; as such they can be considered extensions of the spin connections, and by variation of the action (5) can be obtained in terms of the $(e_\mu^a)^i$ fields. In this work we are interested in exhibit only some of the properties of these kind of actions.

In an earlier version of this manuscript, the contraction of the structure-constant indices with the corresponding Levi-Civita tensors in the space-time and Lorentz sectors was not performed consistently. The action given in equation (5) is the corrected expression for the SU(3) group, and all subsequent derivations and results are based on this revised form.

The construction of an action associated with the SU(2) group would require the introduction of a rank-three tensor with at least two symmetric indices. However, the invariant tensors naturally available in SU(2) are limited to the metric tensor η_{ij} and the completely antisymmetric tensor ϵ_{ijk} . This suggests that additional structures, fields, or assumptions may be necessary in order to formulate an action of the type considered here. We defer such developments to future work. Similar considerations apply to other non-abelian groups, each of which would require a separate analysis of its invariant tensors and algebraic properties. In principle, however, actions analogous to equation (5) could be formulated for each case.

An invariant scalar can be defined as

$$E \sim \varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} \varepsilon_{abcd} d^{mij} (e_\mu^a)^i (e_\nu^b)^j d^{mkl} (e_\rho^c)^k (e_\sigma^d)^l, \quad (7)$$

for the SU(3) non-abelian group. It is plausible that analogous scalar densities can be constructed for other non-abelian groups, although their explicit form will depend on the invariant tensors available in each case [6] and for the specific construction of such an action. They appear to be the appropriate expressions extending e , the standard determinant of the tetrads.

One can also define the action

$$S \sim \int d^4x E d^{ijk} (e_a^\mu)^j (e_b^\nu)^k (R_{\mu\nu}{}^{ab})^i, \quad (8)$$

which resembles action (1) of the Palatini formulation. The equivalence, through the algebra associated to the $(e_\mu^a)^i$ fields, of actions (8) and (5) is left to be presented in future work. These structures are loosely reminiscent of multimetric gravity since multiple tetrad-like fields are naturally present [7].

The ideas developed here should be regarded as preliminary theoretical explorations. Although the physical significance is not yet fully understood, we believe they exhibit sufficiently well defined questions to merit detailed examinations. In particular each non-abelian group naturally leads to the introduction of new fields, which in turn give rise to a “generalized Riemann tensor” and the scalar densities E , playing the role of a generalized square root of a certain matrix determinant. The resulting structure extends the standard geometric framework of gravity. Consequently, the scope of further investigation is not confined to physics alone; but also encompasses mathematical questions related to geometric and group structure.

Similarly one could consider the Ashtekar action [3], promoting the densitized triads to gauge triads $(E^a{}_i)^i$; in this formulation, the associated fields $A_a{}^l$ can be identified as SU(2) gauge fields; following our proposal one would add a further non-abelian group index, namely $(A_a{}^l)^i$. As $A_a{}^l = \Gamma_a{}^l + \beta K_a{}^l$, where $\Gamma_a{}^l$ is the spin connection compatible with the internal SU(2) Ashtekar basis, and $K_a{}^l$ is the extrinsic

curvature which is itself a dynamical field variable, the formulation naturally separates intrinsic and extrinsic geometry contributions, here β is the Barbero-Immirzi parameter. Consequently, when considering $(A_a^l)^i$ fields, they should be understood as being composed of two distinct contributions, $(\Gamma_a^l)^i$ and $\beta (K_a^l)^i$. In this way a proposal analogous to the one presented here for the Palatini action, can also be developed for the Ashtekar action, in which now the index i is related with the $SU(N)$ non-abelian group. A detailed analysis is left for further work.

Another theory which can also be explored within the realm of our formalism is the one due to MacDowell-Mansouri [4]; we outline here the procedure. As is known [8], one departs either from an $SO(4, 1)$ or a $SO(3, 2)$ group, the associated fields are denoted as $\omega_\mu^{AB} = -\omega_\mu^{BA}$, they are subsequently identified as the six components of the spin connection ω_μ^{ab} and the ω_μ^{4a} with the vierbein e_μ^a .

One can now propose $(\omega_\mu^{AB})^i$ in an appropriate extended action, and will identify the gauge fields $(\omega_\mu^{ab})^i$ and $(e_\mu^a)^i$ emerging from extending this ansatz. The analysis is the subject of work to come.

As already argued, at this stage we can only conjecture on the meaning and existence of the gauge fields proposed, the tetrads, spin connections, and even the gravitino field will acquire also an index related to the non-abelian group of interest, the standard $N = 1$ gravitino ψ_μ will now be promoted to its extended $(\psi_\mu)^i$ so, there will be eight of them, for example, associated the $SU(3)$ group. The detailed calculations will be presented elsewhere.

As we know, the relative strength of the electromagnetic, weak, and strong interactions is related to the gauge groups involved; we can only surmise that a similar behaviour is expected here, among standard gravitation and the gauge fields proposed. One can also foresee the extension of the scheme presented here to higher dimensions and larger $SU(N)$ groups and N supersymmetries.

The purpose of this work is to exhibit the possibility of constructing new gauge field structures extending those of gravitation and supergravity. Several routes deserve further exploration, both in physics and in connection with mathematics; a few of them have been mentioned. We have only established a framework that merits further exploration and points in a wide range of directions, some of which may prove to be of relevance in physics, and perhaps also in mathematics. For the moment, we leave the work at the stage of presenting the type of theoretical structures, together with their associated fields, that can be constructed.

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Data availability statement

No data associated in the manuscript.

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